

Figure S1:

The CFR, contact rate, and recovery rate were varied. Disease-free equilibrium(gray), endemic equilibrium(striped), unsustainable (red), and host population crisis(loss of 90%, dark red) regions are shown. For $CFR > 10\%$, smallpox-like features are assumed. For $CFR < 10\%$ SARS-CoV-2/influenza-like features are assumed (these viruses are only distinguished within the model by CFR). Lines within the region bounding endemic equilibrium indicate contours for the percentage of the population infected $(a^* + c^*) \cdot 100$. Darker color corresponds to higher values. Two regions subject to kinetic constraints are outlined. Throughout the main text, the mean time to recovery is 1 week. **A.** Mean time to recovery of 3 days. **B.** Mean time to recovery of 2 weeks.